

Regenerative Agriculture

Inclusive Business Analysis Module

June 2023

idh
transforming markets

About

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In this deck

This deck includes the theory, guidelines and tools for you to apply the **regen ag** module within an Inclusive Business analysis. It assumes you are familiar with the broader methodology, including the Learning Framework, Indicators and Inclusive Business Analysis Financial Model and Case Report. This deck covers below building blocks:

1 Objectives and Learning Questions

Why this module and what do we want to learn about regen ag in relation to business model performance?

2 Key concepts

What is are the bare minimum concepts you need to understand and apply on the interception of regen ag and business?

3 Case Report

How do we report on our regen ag assessment and provide actionable recommendations?

4 Qualitative Assessment

What questions do we ask to assess and score the business model's performance on regen ag

5 Indicators

What are the regen ag-related data points we must collect on every business model to answer our learning questions?

6 Definitions and resources

What definitions and theories are underpinning this module?

01

Objectives & Learning Questions

How to conduct the regen ag module?

Objectives

By applying the **regen ag module** as part of the Inclusive Business analysis, we seek to:

1

Create clarity between actors and across cases on what Regen Ag entails

2

Assess strengths and weaknesses of current Regenerative model applied

3

Demonstrate the business case of Regen Ag for farmers and companies

Learning questions

The **regen ag module** is designed to generate qualitative evidence to answer the below overarching questions

Adoption by farmers

How **complete** is the adoption of Regenerative practices by farmers?

Support by businesses

How well do businesses **enable and support** the transition to Regenerative agriculture?

Key Regen Ag questions that can be answered through other analyses - not part of this module

How do regenerative farm's yields compare to conventional yields?

How do a regenerative farmer's production costs compare to conventional farmers?

How do regenerative SDMs perform compared to conventional SDMs?

Which mechanisms and incentives are used to optimize farmer adoption?

Which timelines are needed for full transition towards regenerative agriculture?

Learning questions and hypotheses

Below learning questions and hypotheses are embedded in the Farmfit Learning Framework

Driver	Question/Hypothesis
RQ_5	What is the relationship between farming practices and risk and resilience at farm level?
RQ_6	What drives farmers to apply certain farming practices?
RQ_9	How do climatic and agro-ecological conditions influence the effectiveness of farm practices and service delivery?
RQ_15	What is the relationship between input service offering and effectiveness at farm level?
RQ_16	What is the relationship between input service offering and farmer resilience?

Primary data collection

Below questions should be collected during primary data collection if the Regen Ag module is planned

Section	Question
12: Income from other crops	During the past 12 months, how much of the [Other crop.1] did you produce?
13: Net income from livestock	Do you grow livestock for commercial purposes?
22: Input costs	In this period, did you use any of the following farm inputs or supplies to take care of the [focus crop]? Seeds and/or seedlings Compost (organic fertilizer) Fertilizer Chemicals (pesticides, herbicides, fungicides) Beneficial insects Pest traps Irrigation (water, irrigation tubes, drip irrigation systems, storage tanks) Other, please specify None of the above I don't know I prefer not to say
26: (Climate) Resilience	Over the past 5 years, did you experience crop losses due to extreme weather events? Out of the past 5 years, in how many years did you experience severe crop losses due to [weather event 1]? On average over the past 5 years, how much of your crops was lost due to [weather event 1]?
Proposed new section: Regen Ag	How many crops do you grow simultaneously on your farm?
	Do you practice intercropping (growing mixed crops on the same field, e.g. in alternating rows)?
	Do you rotate different types of crops over different seasons on the same field?
	Do you grow any crops that fixate nitrogen in the soil?
	Do you maintain any natural areas on your farm that can promote beneficial insects?
	Do you have any practices in place to minimize tillage or soil disturbance?
	Do you have any practices in place that promote keeping the soil covered? Options: Plastic mulching, Organic mulching (leaves, crop stubble, etc.), Cover cropping
	Do you have any practices in place to save water? Options: Precision irrigation, rainwater harvesting

02

**Key
Concepts**

Key concepts

This section includes the essential concepts that require understanding and application as you execute the **regen ag module** within the Inclusive Business analysis

Framework	Purpose
Definition & key principles	...
Farm practices assessment	...
Types of regenerative cropping systems	
Supportive Regen Ag company	

IDH definition of Regenerative Agriculture

One sentence definition

Regenerative Agriculture is a system of farming principles and practices that increase biodiversity, enrich soils, restore watersheds, and enhance ecosystem services (FAO)

Common principles (as selected by IDH*)

Actively regenerate farm and environment^{1,3,4,5,6,8}

Core focus on soil health, but also considering water, biodiversity etc.
^{1,3,4,5,6,8}

Let nature perform farm processes as much as possible, rather than using external inputs^{4,5,7}

Maintain healthy, nutritious, high-yielding crops^{3,5}

Define precise combination of practices based on local context^{3,4,8}

Combine with social activities^{1,3}

One paragraph definition proposed by IDH

*Regenerative Agriculture aims to **actively improve a farm's natural conditions** while maintaining **high-yielding** crops. A **healthy soil** is used as foundation but other outcomes such as biodiversity, carbon sequestration and resilience are also prominent features. Farm processes are solved by **nature as much as possible, rather than using external inputs**. Ideally, Regenerative Agriculture is combined with practices that aim to achieve positive impact on local communities. A precise combination of practices and outcomes is determined pragmatically **dependent on local circumstances, knowledge and priorities**.*

Principles, practices, mechanisms & outcomes

Regen Ag aims to revert the damaging trends from industrial intensification

Industrial intensification

High input, high output

- High costs of production
- High dependency on external inputs
- Soil degradation
- Vulnerable to climate events

Regenerative Agriculture

Low input, high output

- Cost of production minimized
- Many inputs outsourced to natural processes
- Improve soil health
- Resilient to climate shocks

How is this different from other sustainable trends?

Sustainable Intensification

- Focus on high yields but limit environmental harm
- Gray area, what is “limited harm”

Climate-Smart Agriculture

- Any practice that improves climate resilience or relates to carbon
- Widely used terminology, even if one mediocre practice is applied

Organic

- No application of chemical inputs
- Slightly lower yields, often still industrial monoculture

Agroforestry

- Combining crops under a tree canopy, usually no-till
- Only suitable for some crops

Regen Ag requires implementation of practices across 6 categories

Soil cover

Soil disturbance

Diversity

Fertilization

Crop protection

Water management

GAP

Basic Regen Ag

Advanced Regen Ag

	Soil cover	Soil disturbance	Diversity	Fertilization	Crop protection	Water management
GAP	-	Regular tilling, ripping, compaction etc.	-	Apply 4R principles ¹	4R principles ¹ , less toxic inputs	-
Basic Regen Ag	Mulching, limited cover cropping	Less (deep or frequent) tillage than conventional, reduced compaction	2-3 crops polyculture or rotation	4R principles ¹ & less chemical fertilizers & some organic fertilizers	First rely on IPM ² & natural buffers, if insufficient apply chemicals with 4R ¹	Water use does not over-extract available resources; additional practices in place to reduce external water use
			Small natural strips or buffers on farm			
Advanced Regen Ag	Continuous cover – in between crop rows and in between seasons, living cover crops where possible	No till	3+ crop polyculture or rotation	(Nearly) circular nutrient management (e.g. mulches & green manure & crop synergies)	Fully rely on IPM ² & natural buffers, no external inputs applied	Targeted capture and distribution of water; no or sporadic irrigation from off-farm sources
			Extensive natural strips and buffers on farm			
			Integrated livestock			

1: [The 4R Principles of Nutrient Management](#): Right source, Right rate, Right time, Right place; 2: [Integrated Pest Management](#)

Types of regenerative systems

Regenerative agriculture can exist in many different forms, as long as the principles and practices are applied. The most suitable approach depends on local conditions and preferences. A few main types are described below.

Due to the high level of variability in Regenerative systems, some flexibility is required in assessing (scoring) how advanced the system is. Implications of cropping archetypes on the scoring ladder are also given below.

Types of regenerative systems

	Agroforestry	Integration with livestock	Polyculture	Rotational annual crops
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farms combining trees with annual or perennial crops below canopy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combining specific crops with livestock or aquaculture, either directly between the crops or fenced off but with an active role (e.g. converting crop stubble to manure) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simultaneous combination of multiple crops (annual and/or perennial) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monoculture or simple polyculture of annual crops, with changing setup each year (to prevent soil depletion and recurrent pests/diseases)
Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rubber, oilpalm, coconut with food crops under canopy Shade-tolerating plant such as coffee, cocoa under shade trees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Silvopasture (trees + livestock) Leafy crops with aquaculture ponds Rice-fish or rice-duck systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legume + cereal mixes (e.g. maize, beans & squash) Banana, papaya & sweet potato 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rice-wheat rotation Wheat-fallow-alfalfa-potato Wheat-maize-beans
Implications for scoring sheet*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Active mulching is less important in these systems because soils are already relatively protected by tree cover and falling leaves Agroforestry systems are often by default fully rain fed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Livestock may take up an important part in fertilization and crop protection. However, too much/constant livestock can have a negative impact on soil structure 	<i>No particular implications</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Annual crops are often very reliant on tilling. While annual crops can still work well in no-till setups, compromises can exist in reduced frequency or depth of tillage.

*See section Qualitative Assessment

IDH guidance for a supportive Regen Ag company

Guiding principles for a supportive regenerative agriculture company

*A supportive regenerative company **takes responsibility for seeing through the full transition** for farmers towards regenerative farming. Support is provided for **the right amount of time, highly contextualized and based on local consultation**. Synergies such as **resilience, carbon sequestration, ecosystem and social benefits** are pursued. Relationships with farmers are **strong and long-term**; after the intensive transitional support is phased out, **continuous support remains**. Outcomes are **measured and evaluated for continuous improvement**.*

The recommended practices on which a company can be assessed are described in more detail in the next 2 pages

Supportive company assessment: Transition and sourcing

The following tables show which practices need to be in place for basic to more advanced company support in Regenerative Agriculture. This is linked to an in-depth interview to get all the data, and an Excel sheet to attach a score to the assessment, as described in the section Qualitative Assessment

		Supporting the transition				Sourcing and value chain	
		Training	Inputs & materials	Financial incentives	Long term support	Sourcing relations	Market access
Basic		Dedicated multi-year training program, e.g. by field staff and demo plots	Access to required inputs and materials facilitated	Financial grants to support transition, based on joining the program or adopting practices	Intensive transitional support is phased out in a transparent manner; some form of continuous support remains	Long-term contracts with suppliers	Diversification crops chosen with local market access in mind
	Advanced	Continuous capacity building within community, e.g. through peer program; knowledge distribution through many channels (e.g. flyers, mobile apps, radio)	Access to range of various options for inputs and materials, facilitation tailored to farmer segments	Variable incentives, based on needs, outputs (e.g. environmental or linked to carbon scheme)	Continuous long-term support remains in all forms: technical, material and financial	Strong and long-term relationship with buyers, e.g. through collaborative decision-making	Active offtake or support in market access for diversified produce

Supportive company assessment: Planning and co-benefits

The following tables show which practices need to be in place for basic to more advanced company support in Regenerative Agriculture. This is linked to an in-depth interview to get all the data, and an Excel sheet to attach a score to the assessment, as described in the section Qualitative Assessment

		Production planning				Capitalizing on co-benefits*			
		Local consultation	Contextualization	Measurement	Evaluation	Carbon	Ecosystem benefits	Social benefits	Resilience
Basic		Project plans consulted with local people	Cropping system copied from similar regions with some finetuning in local area	Measurement of KPIs after several years	Evaluation of effects to track unintended consequences and correct course	Carbon sequestration and/or emissions qualitatively assessed and stimulated	Benefits of ecosystem benefits qualitatively known and pursued	Due diligence conducted to ensure no harm on community status (e.g. gender balance, nutrition)	Qualitative assessment of resilient production improvements
				Including social, economic and environmental indicators					
Advanced		Extensive co-design of plans by local people	Crops and rotations chosen after in-depth local study and testing	At least annual measurement of KPIs	Periodic evaluation moments planned, both to look out for unintended consequences and to further optimize	Carbon sequestration and/or emissions central to activities; Quantitatively assessed and linked to finance flows	Ecosystem benefits quantitatively assessed and pursued; Linked to finance flows	Intentional design for social improvements	Quantitative assessment of resilient production improvements

03

**Conducting
the
assessment**

How to conduct the Regen Ag module?

When to conduct the Regen Ag interview

This shows a sample timeline of an Inclusive Business analysis. It is advised to populate the scoring tool as you discuss scoping, kick-off and strategy on an ad-hoc basis. Then, have a dedicated Regen Ag interview (1.5 hours) latest during the site visit. Ask only those questions that have not been answered yet

Interview Guidelines

Guidance on what and how to assess, and who conducts the assessment of selected indicators

Who does the assessment?

Analyst or enumerator conducting a country visit to the assessed company. Must be a person **trained for the purpose**.

How to do the assessment?

1. The analyst determines the relevant farmer segments for which to ask the questions
2. The analyst asks for information, **one indicator at a time**, for all relevant segments. The suggested guiding questions can be used.
3. Detailed answers are written down in the interview form
4. Sufficient information must be captured to be able to assess and score the practices later on using the scoring tool. Some additional information is provided under each question to help assess the situation

Screenshot of the Interview Guidance (Word doc)

Interview guidelines – Regenerative Agriculture SDM Module
 This document provides guidelines for an SDM Analyst to interview the SDM operator on Regenerative Agriculture. The answers captured through this document can afterwards be used to fill out the Regenerative Agriculture Ladder Excel sheet.

General info

Number + name of SDM case	
Company name	
Date	
Interviewer name	
Farmer segments relevant for this interview	

Section 1: Farm level
 Ask the following questions for all relevant farmer **segments**

1.1 Soil coverage

Do you have any practices in place that promote keeping the soil covered? If yes, what covers the soil? Do any periods of uncovered soil remain throughout the year?
Segment 1:...

Basic soil cover is with organic materials such as crop residues, leaves etc. that slowly decompose over time. More advanced soil cover is with cover crops in between main crops, which make sure soils always have interactions with living roots (cover cropping can both be in between rows, or on the whole farm in between seasons).

1.2 Soil disturbance

Do you have any practices in place that promote less soil disturbance? If yes, which practices?
Segment 1:...

Soil disturbance includes frequent tillage, ripping, trampling etc. This damages soil structure, fungal networks and microbial balances in the soil that support plant health. Materials and practices exist that till less deep (i.e. only in the top 15cm of the soil) or less frequent. ideal for soil health is a cropping system that can manage with no tillage at all. However, this must be designed and executed carefully to prevent weed growth and soil compaction. Limited compaction means that soils are not constantly grazed or compacted by heavy machinery.

Scoring Tool

Below is a screenshot of the Excel scoring tool that provides all questions and guidance for the analyst to assess the company and get to the final scoring. Scores can then be translated to the respective analysis in the Case Report

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
2	Category	Activity	Basic (2 points)	Advanced (4 points)			Score			Additional info	
3							Segment 1	Segment 2	Segment 3		
6	Farm level	Soil coverage	Mulching with organic materials	Continuous cover - in between main crops immediately cover crops (living roots)			2	3	4	<p>4R principles of nutrient management are designed to optimize input use for plant health and low environmental damage. The are: Right source, Right rate, Right time, Right place of application.</p> <p>Integrated Pest Management here means that in first instance, pests are diminished by preventative measures, such as crop rotations, diversification and stimulating biodiversity for natural predators. If pests do occur at a damaging level, clear plans are in place to mitigate them in the least damaging way</p> <p>Whether irrigation is over-extracting available resources requires a separate assessment; under ideal circumstances the SDM operator has done such an assessment. To assess how important this category is, see e.g. the WWF Water Risk Filter (click the indicator Water Scarcity): https://riskfilter.org/water/explore/map</p>	
7		Soil disturbance	Less (deep or frequent) tillage than conventional, limited compaction	No till, permaculture or agroforestry							
8		Farm diversity	2-3 crops simultaneously or in rotation	Natural buffers; 3+ crop polyculture; Integrated livestock;							
9		Fertilization	Apply 4R principles + reduction of chemical fertilizers + adding organic fertilizers	(Nearly) circular nutrient management (e.g. using mulches, green manure, crop synergies all together)							
10		Crop protection	First rely on Integrated Pest Management & natural buffers, if that is insufficient apply chemicals with 4R	Fully rely on IPM & natural buffers							
11		Water management	Water use does not over-extract available resources; practices in place to reduce external water use (beyond mulching, soil structure, shade)	Targeted capture and distribution of water (e.g. rainwater harvesting, ridging); no or sporadic irrigation from off-farm sources							
12											
13							Total score:	2	3	4	
14							Percentage score:	8%	13%	17%	
15							Evaluation:	No Regen Ag	No Regen Ag	No Regen Ag	
16											
17	Planning	Contextualization	Cropping system copied from similar regions, some finetuning in local area	Crops and rotations chosen after in-depth local study and testing							
18		Local consultation	Project plans consulted with local people	Extensive co-design of plans by local people							
19		Measurement	Measurement of KPIs after several years; Including social, economic and environmental indicators	At least annual measurement of KPIs;							
20		Evaluation	Evaluation of effects to track unintended consequences and correct course	Periodic evaluation moments planned, both to look out for unintended consequences and to further optimize							

How to score

- Total of 20 indicators over 5 categories
- Scoring guidance between 0 and 4 per indicator:
 - 0=Nothing in place on this practice
 - 1=Something in place but not up to the standard described under Basic
 - 2=See description of Basic
 - 3=More than Basic but not fully Advanced
 - 4=See description of Advanced
 - n/a= If the question does not apply in the local context (discuss this with Better Environment first)
- The tool automatically calculates the total score per category, a score percentage and evaluation (Low/Med/High), to be used in the report slides

04

Case Report

Case Report

This section includes the key analysis performed on gender as reported on in the Inclusive Business Case Report.

Analysis	Purpose
Recommendations	Highlight the most important opportunities for improvement that were identified as part of this module
Regen Ag – Farm level assessment	Shows the outcome of the Regenerative Agriculture assessment at farm level, for all relevant farmer segments. It allows you to highlight the main outcomes/remarks/observations (be it positive or negative)
Regen Ag – Business level assessment	Shows the outcome of the Regenerative Agriculture assessment at business level, within 4 separate categories. It allows you to highlight the main outcomes/remarks/observations (be it positive or negative)
(Optional) Quantitative deep-dives: cost-benefit analyses	In case a specific quantitative deep-dive is required. A few possible examples are given.
Farmer P&L	Note: a comprehensive profit & loss analysis of farmer practices, including any regenerative practices, is always part of the core Inclusive Business methodology and case report, and therefore not repeated in this separate module.

Recommendations (option 1) | [Key take-away]

We have identified and prioritised recommendations that [Company] can explore across the highlighted opportunity pathways:

Theme	Recommended next steps	Priority	Effort	Timeline
Regenerative Agriculture	Low soil disturbance: Farmers apply multiple regenerative practices, but still do deep tillage and ripping. Reducing depth and frequency of tillage will further strengthen the results from other practices, among which better water retention and nutrient cycling			1-3 years
	Carbon sequestration: Company has targets in place for carbon reduction and sequestration, but has not yet considered the potential for carbon sequestration in trees and soil as part of their Regenerative Agriculture program.			1-3 years
	Long-term support: Company provides farmers with intensive support and incentive packages to adopt Regenerative Agriculture for 3 the next years. They should timely consider the long-term support that farmers may require afterwards, such as price premiums and continuous field advisory services			>5 years

High Medium Low

Regenerative agriculture - farm practices | [Main message/key take-away of the slide]

* You can find the detailed regenerative agriculture assessment [in the annex](#).

Regenerative agriculture – business support | [Main message/key take-away of the slide]

* You can find the detailed regenerative agriculture assessment [in the annex](#).

Note: both farmer and business P&Ls, including any Regenerative practices when relevant, are done in detail as part of the core Inclusive Business analysis. These assessments are therefore not repeated in this separate module methodology. This slide is only indicative

[Example] Farmer and business P&L

Farmer net income with and without Regen Ag

SDM net income with and without Regen Ag

	PARAMETERS	OBSERVATIONS & GAPS
Farm level	Soil cover	
	Soil disturbance	
	Farm diversity	
	Fertilization	<p style="text-align: center;">Annex slide When: If the regenerative agriculture module is applied</p>
	Crop protection	
	Water use	
Planning	Local consultation	
	Contextualization	
	Measurement	
	Evaluation	

Sources: Company documents and interviews

	PARAMETERS	OBSERVATIONS & GAPS
Co-benefits	Carbon sequestration and emission	<div style="background-color: #fff9c4; padding: 20px; text-align: center;"> <p>Annex slide</p> <p>When: If the regenerative agriculture module is applied</p> </div>
	Climate resilience	
	Ecosystem benefits	
	Social benefits	
Transition support	Training	
	Inputs & materials	
	Financial incentives	
	Long term support	
Sourcing & Value Chain	Sourcing relations	
	Market access	

Sources: Company documents and interviews

05

**Optional
deep-dives**

Deep-dive data requirements

To assess whether Regen Ag is a viable business case for farmers and companies, all costs and benefits should be considered. Many of these will be captured as part of the broader SDM analysis. Below are suggested data requirements for a Cost-Benefit Analysis of a Regenerative Agriculture package.

Example deep-dive analyses: Farm level

Farmer P&L

Farmer P&L - GAP SDM

Farmer P&L - Regenerative SDM

Discussion

A Regenerative farmer initially must invest much more than a regular GAP farmer, particularly in planting materials and equipment. However, after year 3 costs of production become much less than that of a GAP farmer because there are almost no input costs. At the same time produce increases – while maize yields are slightly lower than that of GAP farmers, intercropping with cashew and chickpeas eventually leads to much higher total volumes coming from farms. These effects combined double the net income.

Labour needs

Farmer labour needs - GAP

Farmer labour needs - Regenerative

Discussion

A Regenerative farmer has high labour needs in the first two years, mostly due to initial planting costs of cashew. In subsequent years, planting costs remain high due to intercropping with chickpeas. However, all other labour costs are lower than that of a GAP farmer. Weeding, fertilization and spraying needs are much less. Ploughing is no longer done, but replaced by the less time-consuming task of mulching. Overall labour needs are thus lower for a regenerative farmer after 4 years. But communication and mechanisms need to be in place to cover the initial increased labour needs.

Carbon

Specific calculations

Disclaimer: suggestive information only. For more exhaustive and detailed recommendations a topical expert should be involved.

How Regen Ag influences carbon

Co-benefits of carbon

Quantitative inclusion in SDM

Reduced carbon emission

- Mostly by reduced fossil-based fertilizers

Benefits for companies:

- Reaching carbon targets: Insetting. Elaborate guide on how to approach this as a company: [Insetting 101](#)
- Or, generating an additional income stream: Offsetting. This requires a large scale and third party verification

Total carbon reductions or sequestration can be roughly estimated in SDM reports if proxy data is available. Look for reliable reports that mention emission reduction or sequestration potential in similar cases.

Emissions from fertilizers can be calculated if the amount and type of fertilizer reduction is known, using e.g. [this calculator](#)

Biomass carbon sequestration (trees)

- Carbon is be stored in biomass by growing trees (or other woody plants)

- Benefits to farmers are only indirect: e.g. trees for shade, wind breaks, diversified income

E.g.: "Regenerative Agriculture cotton emits X% less carbon", or "Reduced tillage in wheat increases soil carbon by 0.X% per year"

The amount of carbon stored in wood can be estimated by inserting the amount of trees planted in e.g. [this calculator](#) (approximate only; precise amounts depend on tree type and climate)

Soil carbon sequestration

- Carbon amount in soils is increased by:
 - Less tillage
 - Organic inputs & mulches
 - Biochar
 - More living roots

- Benefits to farmers are only indirect: soil carbon is a general proxy for soil health
- Benefits for companies are limited. There is still unclarity about how much carbon is really being sequestered long term in soils. No verification method yet exists for carbon credits on this.

- Soil carbon is measured via Soil Organic Carbon/Matter (SOC/SOM). This needs expensive lab tests which are impractical at scale. Cheaper equipment that can measure SOC in the field is being developed but not commercially available yet

Climate resilience

How Regen Ag influences resilience

Co-benefits of resilience

Measurement & calculations

Crop diversity

- Increased crop diversity can reduce the impact of a particular climate event on a farmer's income, because if one crop is damaged, the other may not be

Biodiversity

- More abundant biodiversity on a farm can reduce the impact of pest and disease outbreaks, which are expected to increase under climate change

Soil buffering capacity

- A healthy soil can absorb excess water and reduce erosion in case of heavy rainfall, while maintaining water better during heat and drought

Shade

- Trees can provide shade to other crops, making them more heat and drought tolerant

See Climate Resilience Module

See Climate Resilience Module

Ecosystems

How Regen Ag influences ecosystems

Ecosystem benefits

Also known as Ecosystem Services

Measurement & calculations

Biodiversity

- All Regen Ag practices are designed to improve biodiversity

- More abundant biodiversity on a farm can reduce the impact of pest outbreaks
- Increased biodiversity can increase the amount of pollinated flowers and subsequent fruit development

Soil health

- All Regen Ag practices are designed to improve soil health

- As for climate resilience, a healthy soil can absorb excess water and reduce erosion in case of heavy rainfall, while maintaining water better during heat and drought

Water quality

- Reduced chemical runoff from farms and increased filtration in natural buffers leads to higher quality water sources in the surroundings

- Improved water quality improves drinking water and freshwater fish availability

Estimating and calculating the impact of Regen Ag on ecosystem services is difficult even for experts. Co-benefits should only be described in a qualitative manner.

Social standards

How Regen Ag influences social standards

Social benefits

Measurement & calculations

Disclaimer: suggestive information only. For more exhaustive and detailed recommendations a topical expert should be involved.

Food security

- Diversification can lead to a larger variety of crops for local consumption

- Diverse cropping systems likely improve nutritional variety of locally available crops, such as increased protein availability from typically intercropped legumes

Gender equality

- There is a broad call to implement Regen Ag together with programs that aim to increase gender equality; e.g. by providing training for women on managing additional crops

- Improved social equality, besides its moral implications, can increase adoption of coupled Regen Ag services and improve their long-term application

Indigenous people

- There is a broad call to include indigenous people in Regen Ag programs. They are likely to have extensive knowledge on cropping systems and plant species that suit the local environment. Compensation for sharing such knowledge should be provided

- The nutritional value of additional crops can be looked up and coupled to information on local diets and nutritional deficits. For example, [this report](#) shows a vast overconsumption of tubers and insufficient consumption of nuts and legumes in Sub-Sahara Africa.
- Nutritional information in the web is often of low quality; info should only come from highly trusted sources and be verified in the local context.

- Measurement of social improvements is likely to be output-based only (e.g. # women included in trainings)

06

Indicators

Indicators stemming from this module

This section mentions all indicators that are captured as a direct result of the Regen Ag module

Dimension	Data collection	Data storage
Regen Ag Score – Farm level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company interview on Regen Ag (see interview guidelines), for each relevant segment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Full answers in Interview Guide Scores in Scoring Tool Total category score in Indicator tab (Financial Model)
Regen Ag Score – Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company interview on Regen Ag (see interview guidelines) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “”
Regen Ag Score – Supporting transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “”
Regen Ag Score – Sourcing & VC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “”
Regen Ag Score – Co-benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “”
Years since starting Regen Ag	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Full answers in Interview Guide Number per segment in Indicator tab (Financial Model)

Other related indicators

This is a long-list of Regen Ag related indicators collected as part of the Inclusive Business analysis

	Climate resilience lens	Unit	Source	Definition
D3.01.1	Environmental risks - None	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main environmental risks farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.01.2	Environmental risks - Flooding	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main environmental risks farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.01.3	Environmental risks - Heavy rainfall patterns	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main environmental risks farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.01.4	Environmental risks - High temperature or droughts	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main environmental risks farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.01.5	Environmental risks - Pests and disease	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main environmental risks farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.01.6	Environmental risks - Windstorms	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main environmental risks farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.01.7	Environmental risks - Other	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main environmental risks farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.1	Farm management risks - None	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.2	Farm management risks - Damaging pesticide	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.3	Farm management risks - Monoculture practices	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.4	Farm management risks - Over-fertilization	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.5	Farm management risks - Over-irrigation	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.6	Farm management risks - Suboptimal crop variety	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.7	Farm management risks - Under-fertilization	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.8	Farm management risks - Under-irrigation	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.02.9	Farm management risks - Other	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	List of main farm mismanagement practices by farmers in the SDM are facing
D3.03.1	Environmental services - None	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	Main climate services provided by the SDM operator to farmers
D3.03.2	Environmental services - Agroforestry or diversification	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	Main climate services provided by the SDM operator to farmers
D3.03.3	Environmental services - Improved crop varieties	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	Main climate services provided by the SDM operator to farmers
D3.03.4	Environmental services - Insurance	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	Main climate services provided by the SDM operator to farmers
D3.03.5	Environmental services - Integral pest management	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	Main climate services provided by the SDM operator to farmers
D3.03.6	Environmental services - Smart irrigation	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	Main climate services provided by the SDM operator to farmers
D3.03.7	Environmental services - Sustainable input provision	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	Main climate services provided by the SDM operator to farmers
D3.03.8	Environmental services - Other	Yes / No	SDM Analysis	Main climate services provided by the SDM operator to farmers
D3.04	Climate resilience	#	External data	This Go to index summarizes a country's vulnerability (exposure and sensitivity) and readiness (ability to leverage investments and convert them to adaptation actions) to the negative impact of climate change
D3.05	Soil degradation	Qualitative range	External data	This indicator shows the severity of soil degradation in 4 categories: water, wind, physical and chemical deterioration.
D3.06	Water risk	Qualitative range	External data	This indicator identifies areas with water-related risks, based on 12 subcategories such as drought severity, seasonal variability and ground water stress
D3.07	Human footprint	#	External data	The human footprint map measures the cumulative impact of direct pressures on nature from human activities. It includes eight inputs such as buildings, crop land and population density.

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Definitions & Resources

Glossary

Term	Description
4R principles	4R principles of nutrient management are designed to optimize input use for plant health and low environmental damage. The are: Right source, Right rate, Right time, Right place of application.
Green manure	Green manure is a name given to cover crops that provide fertilizing services to the soil; most notably nitrogen fixation. Leguminous plants are the most common example of this, but many other plants also lead to nitrogen fixation (including some vines and trees)
Integrated Pest Management (IPM)	Integrated Pest Management here means that in first instance, pests are diminished by preventative measures, such as crop rotations, diversification and stimulating biodiversity for natural predators. If pests do occur at a damaging level, clear plans are in place to mitigate them in the least damaging way
Mulching	Mulching is the covering of soil with some material to reduce exposure to the elements or evaporation from the soil. Mulching is effective with many types of organic materials, including crop residues, leaves, compost, and wood chips. Consequences such as fire hazards and increase in fungi must be considered. In some cropping systems, plastic sheets are used as mulches, but this is not recommended in regenerative setups.
Natural buffers	Natural buffers are areas on or surrounding a farm that provide a natural resource or service. It could be e.g. strips of native plants for pollinators and natural pest predators, or reeds that filter and absorb excess nutrient and chemical run-off
No till	No till refers to farming without seasonal tillage or ploughing, which breaks natural soil structure and exposes soil to increased erosion. It is aimed to enhance soil health. No till requires additional farming practices to deal with consequences such as weed growth. All crops can and have been grown in no till setups, and literature often exists on results and best practices.
Permaculture	Permaculture is the growing of multiple plants and crops in a way that mimics a stable ecosystem and needs little to no maintenance once mature. It often includes a large amount of perennial plants, but can also include annuals that self-seed in subsequent years.

Term	Description
Agroecology	
CSA	Climate Smart Agriculture has been defined as “agricultural practices that sustainably increase productivity and system resilience while reducing greenhouse gas emissions”. Under this broad umbrella fall things such as soil and water management that can overlap with GAP and Regenerative Agriculture. The main difference with Regenerative Agriculture is that CSA can include single-practice interventions that impact only one or a few components on the farm. These often interfere as little as possible with conventional (industrial) agriculture. For example, adding irrigation to a monocropped, intensive farm could be considered a CSA intervention.
GAP	Good Agricultural Practices are guidance and practices that aim to reach high yielding and quality crops. Common elements are nutrient management (e.g. through the 4R principles), crop protection, irrigation, land preparation, harvest etc. Its main differences with Regenerative Agriculture are that it is typically based on chemical inputs and continuous intensive human management (e.g. ploughing, irrigation), rather than nature-based inputs and services
NBS	
Nature positive	

Further reading

Introduction to Regen Ag

- [NRDC Guide to Regenerative Agriculture](#)

Practical guidance

- [Regenerative Agriculture 101](#)
- [Agrovista Practical guide](#)
- [Farming for a Better Climate](#) (scroll down for various useful factsheets & practical guides)

Company frameworks

- [Unilever guide to Regen Ag](#)
- [Nestlé's RA Framework and guide](#)

Definitions

- [Schreefel et al, compiling definition from 28 articles](#)
- [Giller et al, looking at common principles and practices](#)
- [Newton et al, reviewing definitions from 229 articles](#)
- [Review paper, building on all the before](#)

Thought-provoking articles

- [The Counter: Regen Ag needs a reckoning](#)
- [Offshoot: Can we talk about Regen Ag?](#)
- [Growing Africa: Why the buzz on Regen Ag?](#)

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Annex

IDH Inclusive Business Analysis

offers practical, data-informed insights to **innovate, build and scale** business models towards resilient viable, inclusive value chains.

Scope and study approach

- The Inclusive Business analysis is a business model analysis focusing on the interaction between company and smallholder farmer business case
- Builds on both industry-standard, and tailor-made frameworks and tools: e.g., Business Model Canvas (Osterwalder), P&L, Digital Maturity assessment (KPMG)
- Aggregates wide range of contextual, operational, financial, and agroeconomic data, both qualitative and quantitative
- **Goes broad and deep:** combines cross-sectional data collection with a case study approach*

**A cross-sectional study is a type of research design in which you collect data from many different individuals at a single point in time
A case study is used to generate an in-depth, multi-faceted understanding of a complex issue in its real-life context*

Modularity

Modularity is a design principle that subdivides a product into smaller parts called modules, which can be independently created, modified, replaced, or exchanged with other modules or between different systems.

Due to its modularity the Inclusive Business analysis can:

- Assess a wide range of different companies, value chains and sustainability issues
- Provide insights to different audiences: program and investment managers
- Generate in-depth case study and aggregate benchmarking insights

Modules

We currently have 13 content modules within three categories (greyed out are still to be finalized)

